

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

 OPEN ACCESS

Received: 28/02/2026

Accepted: 06/04/2026

Published: 17/04/2026

Citation: Mahale DS, Kawtikwar V (2026) SmartVulNet: A Comparative Analysis of Deep Learning Models for Smart Contract Vulnerability Detection Using Visual Bytecode Representation. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 19(14): 931-940. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v19i14.306>

* Corresponding authors.

124devyani1001@sjcem.edu.invidyak@sjcem.edu.in**Funding:** None**Competing Interests:** None

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Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](https://www.indjst.org/))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

SmartVulNet: A Comparative Analysis of Deep Learning Models for Smart Contract Vulnerability Detection Using Visual Bytecode Representation

Devyani Suresh Mahale^{1*}, Vidya Kawtikwar^{1*}

¹ Department of Computer Engineering, St. John College of Engineering and Management, Palghar, Maharashtra, India

Abstract

Objectives: This study aims to develop an automated and scalable deep learning framework for detecting vulnerabilities in Ethereum smart contracts by solving the limitations of traditional manual auditing and static analysis methods which mainly suffer from high false positives and limited pattern recognition capability. **Method:** A novel bytecode-to-image transformation pipeline has been designed to convert Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) bytecode into standardized 128×128 grayscale images. Multiple deep learning architectures which were trained and evaluated on a dataset of over 12,000 annotated smart contracts across eight vulnerability classes. SMOTE-based class balancing and multi-class classification techniques which were applied to improve model robustness. **Findings:** Baseline CNN and MobileNetV3-Large has achieved accuracies of 0.75 and 0.39 respectively while EfficientNet-B7 improved performance to 0.77 accuracy. The proposed EfficientNet-B7 + CBAM model has achieved the highest performance with 0.80–0.81 accuracy, 0.80 precision, 0.80 recall and a macro F1-score of 0.79 by showing the performance of attention-guided feature refinement. **Novelty:** The study introduces a language-independent visual representation of smart contract bytecode combined with attention-enhanced deep learning by giving a scalable and quite a good alternative to traditional vulnerability detection approaches in blockchain security.

Keywords: Vulnerability Detection; Smart Contracts; Deep Learning; EfficientNet-B7; Blockchain Security

1 Introduction

The use of blockchain technology has significantly changed how decentralized computing is performed by allowing the execution of digital agreements without the use of trust by employing smart contracts, especially within platforms like Ethereum⁽¹⁾. These self-executing programs eliminate intermediaries in transfer of assets, financial services, and a style of governance⁽²⁾.

Existing vulnerability techniques which includes static analysis and all which mainly suffer from high false positives, inability to capture any complex behavioural patterns. To overcome such loopholes, this study introduces SmartVulNet, which is a deep learning model to translate Ethereum bytecode to standardized grayscale images and identify vulnerabilities with enhanced computer vision architectures. The model achieves better spatial and channel-wise discrimination of features by combining EfficientNet-B7 and Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM). The suggested methodology is tested on more than 12,000 annotated contracts in eight vulnerability types, and counter-measures to a set of baseline architectures are conducted to confirm the quantifiable performances as well as confirm the relevance of the method in scalable, automated smart contract vulnerability detection.

The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

1. A novel methodology for converting EVM bytecode into image representations suitable for deep learning.
2. Integration of EfficientNet-B7 and CBAM tailored for vulnerability detection, enhancing feature discrimination in the visual space.
3. Extensive experiments and ablation studies validating that attention-enhanced models outperform conventional architectures on smart contract vulnerability detection.

1.1 Evolution of Smart Contracts and Security Challenges

Smart contracts were first envisioned by Nick Szabo in the 1990s⁽³⁾ and are self-executable programs that support, check or enforce contracts on blockchain networks without intermediaries⁽⁴⁾. They have been closely connected with the progress of the blockchain technology, especially since the release of Ethereum in 2015 which added a Turing-complete scripting language allowing more complex decentralization applications (DApps)⁽⁵⁾. In the long term, smart contracts have evolved to be more complex protocols that serve decentralized finance (DeFi), non-fungible tokens (NFT)s and supply chains and governance systems⁽⁶⁾. Their spread has emphasized the transformational nature and the risks involved with these applications.

Irrespective of the benefits associated with them (e.g., transparency, immutability, automation), smart contracts are susceptible to numerous security threats because of the presence of coding errors, the presence of logical flaws, and the immutability of blockchain transactions⁽⁷⁾.

The visibility of high-profile attacks, such as the DAO attack in 2016, has made known to everyone how vulnerabilities such as re-entrancy, integer overflow, integer underflow, and access control can be used to drain millions of dollars in digital assets⁽⁸⁾. Moreover there are some multi-contact interactions on DeFi platforms further which create new attack surfaces such as front-running, flash loan attacks and oracle manipulation. Lack of standardized auditing practices, high rate of innovation and low access to formal verification tools to contracts make security issues more complicated⁽⁹⁾.

The development of smart contracts is not only a technological process but is a battle with new security threats⁽¹⁰⁾. There is some recent studies which mainly focus on using automated auditors, formal verification and anomaly detection with machine learning as the means of securing that the risks are mitigated⁽¹¹⁾. Moreover, implementation of the secure coding frameworks and best practices is becoming important to guarantee reliability and user trust in the decentralized ecosystems. This two-fold path, the functionality expansion and the development of security issues is actually an important aspect to understand in increasing scalable, strong and secure smart contract systems⁽¹²⁾.

1.2 Deep Learning in Vulnerability Detection

Recent studies underscore the increasingly important role of automated software vulnerability detection in enhancing both the quality and security of software, as traditional methods in the field of the static analysis may lack efficiency, have a high false alarms, or be unable to scale. To address these limitations, several deep learning based methods have been suggested, each concentrating on various factors of vulnerability representation, dataset design and model structure.

Study⁽¹³⁾ did a critical analysis of the state-of-the-art DL-based vulnerability prediction systems and found that although their model reported accuracies of up to 95, their predictions actually decreased to less than half in actual situations due to factors such as data duplication, imbalanced class distributions and token-level feature learning that mimicked spurious relationships as the names of variables but not the actual vulnerability causes. To solve this, the authors focused on principled dataset design and realistic model training, and obtained the largest possible improvements in both precision and recall (33.57% and 128.38% improvements, respectively, over baselines).

The paper⁽¹⁴⁾ proposed a fine-grained vulnerability detection tool called Vudenc, built based on word2vec embeddings and an LSTM network that identifies vulnerable Python code on a fine-grained level. With 1,009 vulnerability fixing commits of

seven vulnerability types, Vudenc performed well, with recall of 78–87% and precision of 8296, and is not limited to Python, which is a weakness.

Likewise, Study⁽¹⁵⁾ framed the vulnerability detection task as a natural language processing (NLP) problem, where source code is considered as text and advanced deep learning NLP models are used with transfer learning to the English language. The technique, which was trained on more than 100,000 C files containing 123 types of vulnerabilities in NIST NVD/SARD, with an accuracy of over 93 percent, was limited purely by the language-specific nature of its data set.

In⁽¹⁶⁾, the V-CNN was suggested, a CNN-based model that redefines vulnerabilities using CWE/CVE and that reaches 98 percent accuracy, outperforming Random Forest baselines, but would require curated CWE/CVE datasets. Along these lines, Study⁽¹⁷⁾ introduced VulExplore, a CNN+LSTM model that can model spatial and temporal patterns in code metrics, with additional metrics (such as maintainability index and vulnerabilities per line) added, and can achieve precision and recall of 80 or higher and FPR and FNR of 20 or lower, but still requires the use of metric-based representations.

In the study⁽¹⁸⁾ further improved detection was achieved using a better CNNGRU model by integrating the CNN feature extraction and the GRU sequence retention with the assistance of program slicing and vulnerability libraries. This hybrid model showed some training loss rates being 17.2, 10.5 and 7 percent lower than RNN, CNN, and VulDeePecker, however, preprocessing complexity and dependence on vulnerability libraries are problematic. Taken altogether, these papers illustrate that though deep learning can make a vast improvement to automated detection of vulnerabilities by learning complicated patterns in code, the ultimate effectiveness remains reliant on tackling the issue of scale, language heterogeneity, and context, which means that upcoming studies must concentrate on scalable, cross-language, and context-sensitive models as shown in Table 1.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset Description

The dataset used in this paper based on two sources of information. These resources put in place over 12,000 Ethereum smart contracts, including simple and inherited contracts, annotated in eight clearly-defined categories of vulnerabilities. Every Solidity contract was translated into Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) byte code, and further translated into standardized grayscale images of size 128x128 in order to facilitate visual analysis using deep learning. The models could classify the images by facilitating the extraction of structural and semantic patterns within a byte code using this representation. Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) was used to deal with imbalance in the classes in the dataset and ensure that all categories of vulnerabilities are equally represented⁽¹⁹⁾. Binarization of the labels was also done to obtain uniform numerical labels that can be used in multi-class classification⁽²⁰⁾. This real-world contract diversity combined with preprocessing strategies and visual representation provided a good base to train strong vulnerability detection models.

Datasets Links:

<https://ethereum.org/en/developers/docs/smart-contracts/>

<https://github.com/Messi-Q/Smart-Contract-Dataset> (Using Resource 3) The architecture of SmartVulNet starts with a smart contract dataset sourced from Ethereum and GitHub repositories. The feature extraction module compiles solidity code into bytecode and then it converts it into grayscale images⁽²¹⁾. This system is finally outputting the predicted vulnerability as shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing was a very important step in preparing the dataset for good model training. Since the smart contract bytecode was transformed into image representations, all images were standardized to a fixed size of 128x128 pixels using OpenCV, ensuring uniformity in input dimensions and compatibility with deep learning architectures. However, the dataset exhibited significant class imbalance, with certain vulnerability categories being underrepresented.

To address this issue and avoid model bias toward majority classes, the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied, generating synthetic samples for minority classes and creating a balanced dataset across all vulnerability categories. Additionally, categorical labels representing different vulnerability types were converted into machine-readable form using the Label Binarizer, which transformed textual class labels into binary vectors suitable for multi-class classification. These preprocessing steps—image resizing, class balancing, and label encoding—ensured consistency, improved generalization, and enhanced the robustness of the deep learning models in accurately detecting vulnerabilities

Table 1. Summary of Existing Studies on Vulnerability Detection

Ref.	Proposed Model / Tool	Dataset / Input	Results	Key Challenges / Limitations
(13)	Realistic DL-based vulnerability prediction	Existing datasets with vulnerabilities, examined real-world performance	Up to 33.57% boost in precision and 128.38% boost in recall over baselines	Performance drops >50% in real-world; models learn spurious features (e.g., variable names)
(14)	Vudenc (DL-based vulnerability detection)	1,009 vulnerabilityfixing commits (7 types: SQLi, XSS, XSRE, RCE, etc.)	Recall: 78-87%, Precision: 82-96%, F1: 80-90%	Focused only on Python; generalization across languages uncertain
(15)	NLP-based vulnerability detection	100,000+ C files from NIST NVD/SARD, 123 vulnerability types	Over 93% accuracy	Limited to C dataset; may not generalize across languages or unseen vulnerabilities
(16)	V-CNN	CWE/CVE-based redefined datasets	98% accuracy, higher than Random Forest (95%)	Relies on predefined CWE/CVE datasets; adaptability to new vulnerabilities limited
(17)	VulExplore	Reconstructed CM dataset (incl. maintainability index, vulnerabilities per line)	FNR/FPR <20%, Precision & Recall >80%	Based only on code metrics, not raw source code; may miss complex vulnerabilities
(18)	Improved CNN+GRU model	Vectorized static code features from slicing; vulnerability library	Training loss rate: 17.2% lower than RNN, 10.5% lower than CNN, 7% lower than VulDeePecker	Relies on vulnerability libraries; preprocessing adds complexity; zero-day adaptability limited

2.3 Training Process

The model training started with compilation based on the categorical cross-entropy loss function, Adam optimizer, and accuracy as the main measures. The reason this setup was selected is that the dataset is a multi-class classification challenge, and categorical cross-entropy is useful in working with several output classes, and Adam provides adaptive learning rates which contribute to improved convergence stability.

The training was carried out with 20 epochs with a batch size of 64, which was also efficient in using the computational resources, and also in balancing the gradients and convergence speed. In the process, a learning rate scheduler was used namely the ReduceLROnPlateau callback that automatically decreased the learning rate when the validation accuracy leveled off thus enhancing model fine-tuning during subsequent epochs.

Such a dynamic tuning helped avoid stagnation and enter further into the optimal weights. The advancement of training was observed through the training and validation error curves, which allowed identifying an overfitting or underfitting tendency. The systematic design made sure that the model kept refining its parameters as the epochs went by hence making the generalization better. Accuracy and loss plots, confusion matrices, and classification metrics were used as the final performance assessment tools and gave a detailed perception of the model in terms of detecting vulnerabilities in smart contracts.

2.4 Data Balancing

Figure 2 presents the class distribution of smart contract vulnerabilities before applying the SMOTE balancing technique.

Figure 3 illustrates the class distribution of vulnerabilities after applying the SMOTE technique. Unlike the imbalance observed earlier, the dataset is now balanced across all categories, with each class containing 426 samples.

2.5 Proposed Model

The proposed framework suggests a novel deep learning architecture that is an EfficientNet-B7 with CBAM that can enhance vulnerability detection of smart contracts. The EfficientNet-B7 model was selected because it has a compound scaling strategy that ensures that network depth, width, and resolution are balanced, and the features can be obtained with a much smaller number of parameters in comparison to classic CNNs. CBAM was introduced to representational learning to further improve it with sequential channel and spatial attention to indicate the most informative section of the bytecode images. The architecture is EfficientNet-B7 with ImageNet weights and then trained on smart contract data that includes CBAM block, Global Average Pooling and fully connected dense layers with multi-class softmax activation. The composition enables the model to selectively

Fig 1. Architecture of the study

Fig 2. Data Balancing before SMOTE

Fig 3. Data Balancing after SMOTE

focus on the patterns of vulnerabilities and minimise noise because of inappropriate nature of the bytecode. The experimental results demonstrated that the proposed EfficientNet-B7+CBAM outperformed the baseline models, and it was able to achieve an accuracy of 81 that proved the performance of attention-driven DL in the specified field.

2.6 Justification of Chosen Models

In this study, there are five DL models were chosen to detect smart contract vulnerabilities. A simplified CNN was added to test the strength of basic feature extraction on bytecode images so that it can be compared with other more complicated models. The rationale behind using VGG16 is that it is a common example of transfer learning model which has a high score in terms of performance in image classification tasks, and it allows one to reuse features of large datasets⁽²¹⁾. MobileNetV3-Large was added because it had to be lightweight and computationally efficient, as it is appropriate in resource-constrained environments. EfficientNet-B7 because of its compound scaling strategy that balances the depth, width, and resolution that provide better accuracy without overutilizing the parameters. Lastly, the EfficientNet-B7 with CBAM was used to evaluate the importance of attention mechanisms to boost features representations by guiding the model to spatially and channel-wise informative area of the bytecode images. These models collectively can offer a wide range of complexity, scalability and performance, making a wide comparison and illustrating the cumulative advantages of attention-based improvements to vulnerability detection.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Model Performance

Fig 4. Performance Comparison of DL Models

The bar chart in Figure 4 provides a visual comparison of five deep learning models across four performance metrics. The x-axis represents the models (CNN, MobileNet V3 Large, VGG16, EfficientNet B7, and EfficientNet B7 with Attention), while the y-axis ranges from 0.0 to 0.9, showing metric values. CNN achieves balanced scores around 0.75, whereas MobileNet V3 Large performs poorly, particularly in accuracy (0.39). VGG16 maintains consistent performance at 0.72, while EfficientNet B7 improves further with 0.77. The best results are achieved by EfficientNet B7 with Attention, consistently reaching 0.80 across metrics.

3.2 Confusion matrices

Figure 5 shows the confusion matrix of the CNN classifier by showing the correspondence between true and predicted vulnerability labels. The values were obtained after training the model for 20 epochs using categorical cross-entropy loss and the Adam optimizer. While CNN achieved reasonable overall accuracy (0.75) the confusion matrix which shows misclassifications across multiple classes.

Figure 6 shows the confusion matrix of the MobileNet V3 Large model which has obtained after training with the same parameters as other models. The results shows weak performance, with many misclassifications across categories.

Fig 5. Confusion matrix of CNN

Fig 6. Confusion matrix of MobileNet V3 Large

Figure 7 shows the confusion matrix of the VGG16 model which has generated after training on the balanced dataset for 20 epochs. Compared to CNN and MobileNet V3 Large VGG16 has showed better generalization with an overall accuracy of 0.72. However there are some challenges which remain as misclassifications which occurred across several classes.

Figure 8 shows the confusion matrix of the EfficientNet B7 model after training with balanced data. The model has achieved strong performance with an accuracy of 0.77 by showing improved predictions compared to CNN, MobileNet V3 Large and VGG16.

Figure 9 shows the confusion matrix of the EfficientNet B7 with Attention model which achieved the highest performance among all tested architectures with an accuracy of 0.80. The matrix shows strong predictions across most classes like 43 correctly identified in class 1 and 41 in class 2 while also reducing misclassifications compared to earlier models.

Fig 7. Confusion matrix of VGG16

Fig 8. Confusion matrix of EfficientNet B7

Fig 9. Confusion matrix of EfficientNet B7 with Attention

3.3 Discussion

According to the SmartVulNet framework, it achieves a maximum accuracy of (0.80-0.81) compared to the traditional baseline models (CNNs, VGG16, MobileNetV3) and prior studies using either handcrafted features or language-independent representations. The use of visual bytecode representation makes it possible for the model to detect significantly more advanced structures in comparison with the V-CNN⁽¹⁶⁾ and VulExplore⁽¹⁷⁾ models that were created with developer datasets or performance metrics.

There are certain limitations to this method. The use of the EfficientNet-B7 architecture causes the computational complexity of this approach to rise considerably, and therefore is less suited for applications where there are limited resources or need for real-time operation. Additionally, converting from a byte code to an image representation creates additional processing costs.

Accuracy and efficiency relate. Lightweight models such as MobileNet are faster for inference, but provide a less than adequate level of performance. On the other hand, using an attention model can make the results of the proposed method closer to the level of accuracy and robustness necessary for performing critical security functions requiring a higher than acceptable computational cost to execute.

4 Conclusion

This study introduced SmartVulNet, a deep learning framework on vulnerability detection on Ethereum smart contracts by means of visual representation of the bytecode. The strategy allowed the classification of multiple classes of vulnerabilities based on the 128x128 grayscale images but with sophisticated computer vision models by converting EVM bytecode into standardized images. Experimental analysis of over 12000 annotated contracts showed that there were definite performance variations amongst architectures. CNN and MobileNetV3-Large were at 0.75 and 0.39 whereas EfficientNet-B7 was at 0.77 accuracy. The overall performance of the proposed EfficientNet-B7 with CBAM attention was the highest with an accuracy of 0.80-0.81, precision of 0.80, recall of 0.80, and macro F1-score of 0.79, which validates the hypothesis that attention mechanisms can improve the feature discrimination and inter-class confusion of the system. The originality of the work consists in the systematic pipeline of the transformation of bytecode to image, the integration of attention-augmented EfficientNet, and the general comparative analysis that proves the quantifiable improvements in relation to the baseline models. This visual abstraction, as opposed to either a static analysis or a hand-written opcode-based tool, provides an understanding of structural patterns without reliance on a vulnerability library, and is more scalable. Applicability of real-time applicability is further established in practice by a Flask-based web application. Future work must consider models of lightweight transformers, hybrid CNN-graph, and explainable AI, and semi-supervised solutions to zero-day vulnerabilities and enhance the efficiency of large-scale blockchain auditing.

5 Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Author Contributions: Devyani Suresh Mahale contributed to the conceptualization of the study, dataset preparation, bytecode-to-image preprocessing, model training, and drafting of the manuscript. Prof. Vidya Kawtikwar supervised the research, provided guidance on methodology design, and contributed to review and editing.

6 Funding

No funding was received for this study.

7 Data Availability

The datasets used in this study are available upon request.

8 Declarations

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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